

8T – Refuting Quark Waves

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, with emphasis on the arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, alongside the primordial equation of coupling constants that regard bosons as net curvature of discrete amounts on the metric tensor, it is possible to refute Quarks to behave as waves. That is because it is impossible to manipulate the spin of Quark triplet, in contrast to manipulating the spin of Bosons configuration due to additional Bosons added, also known as Particle wave duality.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of arbitrary variations which vanish into matter.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

as the amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish. δg
Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we can derive the existence of fermions

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Given four elements distinct:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Then the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need even amounts of equal elements of pluses and minuses. The amount must be even and summed as zero, ensuring stationary Lorentz manifold. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will exclude this result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish to zero. As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$\mathbf{O}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_1 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$\mathbf{Y}: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps. So:

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

That was the construction presented in the 8T thesis. Now as you probably know the manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

We were able to explain the particle wave duality by adding a photon as a result of measurement. The added photon does vary the overall spin configuration from Bosonic to non-Bosonic, as presented in the form of equations (1.44) to (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

$$\left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.46)$$

Since the Quark triplet is bounded and there could not be a quark unbounded, as those are vanishing in pairs, in contrast to the Bosons which are net curvature unbound, it is possible to refute that the Quarks will behave as waves, it is impossible to manipulate each Quark as did with the Bosons spin, if the Quark triplet was unbounded the situation was different but as we know that is not the case. Therefore, in the 8T, despite the fact that the theory allow PW duality to bosons due to spin variance by measurement, the theory allows refutes Quarks to behave as waves, only as particles. That is because it is impossible to manipulate their spin – individual Quarks are confined as they are part of sea of Gluons.

To roll a quark uphill an infinite curve is at the verge of impossible. The attempt to roll the quark triplet elements uphill will eventually lead to a quark reaching the minima, lowest point on the curve. Similar to other physical phenomena aspiring minima.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)